

What Makes the University Irreplaceable?

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The university is under attack. Revisionist powers seek to dramatically alter the role and shape of the university in contemporary societies. A key source of their leverage lies in their ability to exploit a longer-term crisis of the university that has gradually eroded its legitimacy. This paper proceeds in three steps. First, it situates the current crisis of the university within broader structural contexts. Second, it identifies eight concrete processes of institutional erosion. Third, it formulates a central challenge that condenses these dynamics.

I. Three plus one Megatrends

The term megatrends here alludes to dynamics that can be observed globally and have been taking place in multigenerational time horizons. The first three megatrends discussed below are structural in nature and the fourth represents a political reaction to these structural transformations. The scale and scope of these developments challenge the reflexive and decision-making capacities of societies in general and of universities in particular.

Inequality

Climate Change

Digitization

Revisionism

1. Inequality

Rising inequality is a global phenomenon. Over the past forty years economic inequality in industrialized societies throughout the world has increased. Trends in social mobility have reversed. The German sociologist Oliver Nachtwey has described this as the Abstiegsgesellschaft: “The dominant mode of social mobility has gone from upward to downward. Ours is now a society of decline, precarity, and polarisation” (Nachtwey 2018).

Politically no coherent strategies for addressing rising inequality have emerged.

2. Climate Change

Climate Change challenges the capacities of collective action. Unfolding both more rapidly than projected and slower than political systems typically operate, climate change threatens to overwhelm decision-making processes with non-reversible and long-term effects altering the livelihood of large groups of people.

Climate Change up to 2024 had brought forward an unprecedented level of international coordination (Carbon pricing, Paris Accords) resulting in visions of new industrial policies like the Green New Deal. At the same time, climate change has become a flashpoint for revisionist political realignments.

3. Digitization

Digital media change how power works and how both private and collective goods are produced, disseminated and consumed. It enables both new forms of distributing power and goods as well as concentrations of power in hitherto unknown dimensions. AI as the current latest step in digitization in particular exhibits a dramatic dynamic of concentrating power overriding the last remnants of earlier narratives that framed digital networks as inherently decentralizing.

Political answers to Digitization have been largely naïve, driven by hypes while lacking profound understanding of the function, possibilities and dangers of digital technology. Politics but also civil society have failed to develop visions and to communicate how progressive digital societies could look like.

4. Revisionism

Since 2015 Revisionism has emerged as a dominant force in many democratic societies of the western sphere and beyond. After the Brexit and Trumps first presidential term this dynamic has consolidated throughout Europe as well as in Israel and India and parts of Latin America. With Trumps second term aggressive revisionism is in power in the largest economy of the world actively promoting reactionary policies domestically and internationally.

Politically central Europe has escaped Revisionism either by procedural tricks (France) or by coalitions further eroding public trust (Germany). Currently progressive, liberal and center-right forces are unable to set agendas and remain in reactive modes versus revisionist actors: neither political nor cultural visions for transforming the status quo have been convincingly articulated.

II. Erosion of the University

The following eight aspects describe processes which erode the trust in the university as an institution and in sciences in general. Some of these processes have been long underway, some are more recent developments.

1. Social Mobility

Universities are failing to be institutions enabling social mobility: a university degree does not guarantee social mobility anymore. Especially in Anglo-Saxon countries with high tuition fees the cost-benefit calculation in a life-course is no longer given and the mobility-promise inherent to the university is challenged by student debt. At the same time the role of family assets in access to universities has increased again: rather than mitigating inequality universities facilitate it.

2. Credentialization

Randall Collins diagnosis of a “credential crisis” (Collins 1979) remains highly relevant. Sociological research on education shows that, especially in fields such as finance, law and consulting high-prestige credentials tend to matter more than skills and knowledge (Reitz 2017, compare Binder 2016, Rivera 2015). This is further exacerbated by the tactical exploitation of credentials (esp. management of differences) by already culturally, socially and economically privileged members of

marginalized groups which the American Philosopher Olúfẹ́mi Táíwò has described as “elite capture” (Táíwò 2022).

3. Secondary Politization

Universities have become financially reliant on third-party funds attained via (bureaucratic fictions of) marketized competitions. This results in a *secondary politization of science* since universities and researchers need to align their agendas towards current trends and hypes favored by politicians and grant-giving institutions in control of funding. Here the freedom of science is subtly but systematically contaminated by politically structured incentives. This process erodes trust in the independence of the university as an institution.

This hidden political dimension has recently been revealed in the USA by the defunding put in place via DOGE and by the “Fördergeld-Affäre” in Germany

4. AI and Writing

Universities and formalized education facilitate learning and study as initiation through reading and more importantly writing. AI radically alters this relationship: on the one hand Large Language Models (LLMs) automate reading and writing, devaluing the individual effort necessary to engage in these activities while studying and doing research. On the other hand, AI levelled the difference between the written and spoken word in platform environments. This Platform Orality (Engemann 2025) makes oral performances in online video like Youtube, TikTok and Instagram searchable and renders oral formats into attractive alternatives to engage with discourses: listening supplants reading.

Through AI *writing as an initiation into knowledge and reflection* is devalued with unclear consequences for the formation and dissemination of knowledge and reflective capacities.

5. Publication regimes

Academic writing has become the basic material of a rent-seeking publishing industry. The simultaneous capture of the publication dimension and its reputation-economic position by publishers (formalized in Germany by the DEAL-Konsortium) furthered the asymmetry between the university as an institution tasked with the control and dissemination of knowledge and economic actors. In particular, the DEAL-contracts have given publishers the rights to aggregate data via AI, Graph-analysis, bibliometrics and other computational means, enabling an enclosure of an important dimension of scientific activity that becomes inaccessible to the university themselves.

6. Parallel publication contexts

In fields like AI, computer science and parts of STEM parallel publication contexts like ArXiv/BioRxiv/Github etc. have emerged. Here community-driven replication and implementation processes as well as commentary undercuts the timeframes of peer-reviewed research resulting in shorter cycle times and de-facto higher reach and significance than traditional journals and publishers.

These parallel publication contexts partially are funded and based within universities, partially exists in parasitic relations to them. They have become essential in managing reputation and visibility especially in AI and computer science.

7. Replication crisis

In several positivist fields like psychology, economics and medicine more than 60% of studies cannot be replicated challenging the status of these disciplines as sciences. This challenges the epistemic status of these disciplines and undermines the authority of the university as an arbiter of truth. The replication crisis hence is a structural problem affecting the status of the university as a whole and necessitates a proactive engagement with questions of epistemology, methodology and critique.

8. AI & leveraging information asymmetry

The current mode of AI based on compute and data intense models facilitates further concentration of already highly centralized platform digital power. With extreme cap-ex involved and unclear monetization perspectives AI threatens to lead to a “last-man-standing-market” with one or two large platforms surviving and becoming dominant. These vendors would be able to yield yet unseen dimension of information asymmetry due to their capacity to integrate large amounts of data. For the education and research sector a new threat of asymmetry emerges: platform-provided lifelong learning companion-agents capitalizing on the exploitation of ever-increasing information asymmetry they themselves create.

III. Challenge: What makes the University irreplaceable?

In the face of above’s challenges, the fundamental question to be raised becomes *what makes the university irreplaceable?* Why is it indispensable? And do we (whoever this we may be) actually know what this irreplaceability is?

Unless the university, in all its diverse institutional forms, will be able articulate and defend what makes it irreplaceable and uniquely valuable, it is danger to become a historical relict.

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